

Mass multiplication of *Metarhizium anisopliae* on different media

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Original Research Article Received on March 18, 2020 Revised on March 27, 2020 Accepted on April 21, 2020 Published on April 29, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Ankush Taliyan, Ajay Kumar, Rajendra Singh, Rohit Rana, Shekhar Rana</p> <p>Corresponding Author Email singhrajendra0113@gmail.com</p>	<p>Entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) <i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i> are fungal species that is the frequently occurring and destructive pest management to the pathogenic soil and insects. The effect of different substrates for the mass production of <i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i> spore/ml was significantly higher recorded. The results revealed that all the treatments were significantly producing spore per ml and thus increasing the yield significantly as compared to other substrates. The results revealed that all the treatments were significantly higher effective in producing spore/ml as compared to other substrates overall finding showed that substrate tested, for <i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i> spore/ml production was significantly higher recorded 240.53 and 195.26 spore/ml were recorded on substrate irrespective of the temperature.</p>
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Entomopathogenic fungi (EPF) are fungal species that are pathogenic to insects. These fungal pathogens play a vital role in insect population dynamics making it the earliest insect pests control agents. Earliest farmers rely on the actions of predators, pathogens and host plant resistance for the control of insect pests until the discovery of insecticide. The first ground breaking field trials with EPF started with a Russian microbiologist, Elie Metchnikoff in 1888, who later became a Nobel Prize winner and named *Metarhizium anisopliae* (more recently named *M. brunneum*) (Vega *et al.*, 2009). Metchnikoff mass produced fungal conidia on sterilized brewer's mash and combine cultures with sand granules for spreading on field crops.

Many insect pathogenic fungi based bio-insecticides have been formulated and commercially manufactured (Hafiza *et al.*, 2014). The application of EPF in biological control is increasing largely because of greater environmental awareness, food safety concerns and the failure of conventional chemicals due to an increasing number of insecticide resistant species (Shahid *et al.*, 2012). Different substrates of vegetable origin can be used to mass produce conidia, such as different forms of potato, wheat, soy, rice, and bran. Studies by (Dorta and Arcas, 1998) show that rice is a good medium to mass multiply *M. anisopliae* because it provides nutrients and a large surface area on which conidia can be produced.

Conidial production using rice as a substrate is approximately 1×10^9 conidia g⁻¹ (Barajas *et al.*, 2010). The most used solid substrate is parboiled rice (pre-cooked) it is very expensive (Kruger *et al.*, 2014) and thus increases the final selling price. It is recommended that the objective of the production process be low cost and high yield of viable virulent and persistent propagules (Kassa *et al.*, 2008). Mass production of the selected fungi is a necessary prerequisite for any large-scale field application. However, most of these novel systems have not yet been exploited in agricultural practice on a commercial scale. Hence lack of reliable substrates was found to be another major constraint in the mass production. Every living organism requires food for the growth and reproduction; fungi are not exception to it. Fungi secure food from the substrates upon which they live in. All media are not equally good for all fungi nor there universal substrates, upon which all fungi grow. Faster and luxuriant growth of all the fungus can only be obtained when grown on suitable substrate. Locally available and agricultural wastes were found to be excellent substrates for on farm production of antagonists. This helps for large scale delivery to the infection court. Grains or seeds contain varying amount of proteins and carbohydrates, composition of seeds may probably influence the mass multiplication.

Hence, an attempt was made to determine the most suitable and locally available substrate use for the mass multiplication of the fungus. With the current thrust on sustainable agriculture and organic farming, the use of botanical products as pesticides has acquired greater significance. Implementation of environmental friendly agricultural practices is essential for the preservation of the quality of life on earth, eco-friendly and have no residual effect on agriculture produce. Keeping in mind the above facts the present investigations

Materials and Methods

The present investigations storability of *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Metschnikoff) was studied at two conditions, under room temperatures/ambient and freezing at 4°C with two solutions *i.e.* liquid solution and of wettable powder in laboratory at Biocontrol Research Laboratory, Department of Entomology, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel University Agriculture and Technology, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India.

The material and methods employed for these studies are presented in this paper. Aluminium trays, inoculation needles, laminar flow cabinet, petridishes, glass slides, plastic tubs, glass jars, tissue paper, sterilized cotton, test tubes, pipettes, B. O. D. incubator, polythene bags, pins, ocular and stage micrometer, binocular microscope, binocular microscope with photographic facility, spirit, spirit lamp, and disinfectants were made available in Biocontrol Laboratory of Department of Entomology, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel University Agriculture and Technology, Meerut, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Experimental Details

To evaluate the different substrate for Mass production of entomopathogenic fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae* on solid and liquid substrates a plan of field experiment was carried out for the year 2018-19 are details 11 treatments, replication three and design CRD.

Nucleus Culture

The nucleus culture of *Metarhizium anisopliae*, was thereafter maintained on Sabouraud Dextrose Broth (SDB) medium as per the procedure of (Prasad *et al.*, 2014) Briefly, SDB was prepared and sterilized at 121°C (15 lbs) for 20 minutes. Then cooled and poured in presterilized Petri plates and *Metarhizium anisopliae* from stock culture was inoculated aseptically. The Petri plates were incubated at $25 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ in BOD incubator for two weeks to harvest the inoculums culture. Solution of *M. allisopliae* For the isolation of the entomopathogen, a number of diseased *H. armigera* larvae with dense coating of dark green fungal growth were collected from cotton fields at the bio-control laboratory, Meerut in *rabi* 2019-20. Isolation was done by the standard method on potato dextrose agar. Out of 19 samples only one showed the mycelial growth which was later, identified as *M. anisopliae*. Identification was done on the basis of external symptoms, morphology of spores and sporulating structures (Radha *et al.*, 1955, Gopalakrishnan and Narayanan, 1988).

Cultural Media

Sporulation of *M. anisopliae* was subjected to assessment in five liquid cultural media, *viz.*,

Sabouraud's Dextrose Broth + Yeast medium (SDB+Y), Emerson's Yeast Phosphate Soluble Starch (YPSS), Potato Dextrose Broth (PDB), Czpeck's and Barner's medium at four temperature regime, viz., 20, 25, 27 and 30°C. One ml pure fungal suspension from 7-day-old culture (108spores/ml) was inoculated in 100 ml of each autoclaved medium in 250 ml conical flasks in four replications. Cultures incubated for 10 days in BOD incubator at pre decided temperature levels were subjected to spore count studies with haemocytometer.

Spore Counting

A drop of conidial suspension of *Metarhizium anisopliae* (obtained from the growing media by filtering through muslin cloth) was placed on the hemocytometer. The cover glass was put over the grid carefully so that no air bubble entered between cover glass and slide. The conidia of entomopathogenic fungi were counted under Olympu microscope.

Preparation of Fungi

The cultured in SDA medium and kept 10 days at 25±1°C, 100% RH and 12:12 (L:D) photoperiod, Then conidia were harvested and suspended in Tween 80 (0.2 ml/L) in sterile distilled water and vortexes for 3 min to produce a homogenous suspension. Then the suspension was filtered through several layers of cheesecloth to remove mycelia and debris. By using a Haemocytometer, the spore concentration was determined and adjusted 10⁴conidia/ml-1.

Morphological and Biometrical Characters of *M. Anisopliae*

Mycelial, conidiospore and conidial characters were studied by observing the petriplate culture under binocular microscope in laboratory conditions. The culture was grown under ambient condition (average temperature of 27 ± 2°C with RH of 85 per cent) in laminar flow cabinet. Autoclaved potato dextrose agar in petri plates was inoculated with *M. anisopliae* culture. The inoculation was made in the centre of the petridishes and incubated at 20°C in the incubator. In the same manner 10 petridishes were prepared and utilized for recording

the biometrical and morphological characters of *M. anisopliae*.

Determination of Colony Forming Units/ml

Volume of 60 ml of the already prepared potato dextrose cultured *M. anisopliae* inoculums was made up to 100 ml and grinded homogenously with the help of mechanical blender. The grinded material was filtered through UV sterilized muslin cloth. A drop of suspension was released in between a graduated portion of "Neubauer hemacytometer" and the cover slip. The numbers of conidia in each of the 100 randomly selected squares were counted. The CFU/ml was determined with the help of following formula:

$$\text{Standardization of CFU/ml} = \frac{\text{Number of CFU observed} \times \text{dilution factor}}{\text{Number of squares observed} \times 1/1/(4 \times 10^8)}$$

Viability of CFUs

The method used for the purpose was as suggested by Ming Guage Feng the autoclaved potato dextrose agar medium in petridishes (100 mm diameter) was inoculated with the help of micropipette by releasing 0.1 ml *M. anisopliae* suspension, other petridishes with medium were prepared in similar manner and inoculated with various dilution in the series (10¹ to 10¹⁰ CFU/ml) and incubated at 27±1°C. After 48 hrs colony count was recorded.

Statistical Analysis of Data

The data recorded during the course of investigation were subjected to statistical analysis by using analysis of variance technique (ANOVA) for randomized block design as suggested by (Panse and Sukhatme, 1978).

Results and Discussion

Mass Production of *Metarhizium anisopliae*

The effect of different substrates for the mass production of *Metarhizium anisopliae* spore/ml was significantly higher recorded showed that in (table 1). The results revealed that all the treatments were significantly producing spore per ml and thus increasing the yield significantly as compared to other substrates.

The results revealed that all the treatments were significantly higher effective in producing spore/ml as compared to other substrates. Data recorded on 7 day after the day after inoculation of various treatments in the table and figure. T₁₀ sorghum + vermicompost was the best treatment by bringing down the *M. anisopliae* production up to (50.20) spore/ml in liquid medium during the 2018-19 years.

The other treatments in order of spore producing was with T₇ sorghum + vermicompost, 50.20 spores/ml, T₆ sorghum + farmyard manure (FYM) 40.15 spores/ml, T₁ maize + farm yard manure (FYM) 28.10 spores/ml, T₈ sorghum + cow dung (fresh) 23.50 spores/ml, T₂ maize + vermicompost 18.95 spores/ml, T₃ maize + cow dung (fresh) 16.35 spores/ml, T₁₀ sorghum + molasses 10.80 spores/ml, T₅ maize + molasses 7.19 spores/ml, T₉ sorghum + cow urine 5.80 spores/ml, T₄ maize + cow urine 5.70 spores/ml and T₁₁ sorghum + corcyra rearing waste material of sorghum (check) 2.15 spores/ml, dung (fresh) respectively. Overall result showed that among the media tested, *Metarhizium anisopliae* spore/ml production was significantly recorded on the 14 days after higher 50.20 and 40.15 spore/ml were recorded on different medium for mass production of *M. anisopleae*.

Similar trend was recorded on fourteenth day after inoculation. T₇ sorghum + vermicompost again was the most effective treatment (89.10 spore/ml) producing. The second most effective treatment was, T₆ sorghum + farmyard manure (FYM) 74.15 spores/ml, T₁ maize + farm yard manure (FYM) 74.15 spores/ml, T₁ sorghum + cow dung (fresh) 71.19 spores/ml, T₈ sorghum + cow dung (fresh) 61.70 spores/ml, T₂ maize + vermicompost 47.70 spores/ml, T₃ maize + cow dung (fresh) 37.40 spores/ml, T₁₀ sorghum + molasses 26.15 spores/ml, T₅ maize + molasses 16.38 spores/ml, T₉ sorghum + cow urine 5.15 spores/ml, T₄ maize + cow urine 17.80 spores/ml, and T₁₁ sorghum + corcyra rearing waste material of sorghum (check) 7.80 spores/ml, during both the year 2019-20 respectively.

The observation data recorded twenty one days after inoculation trend during the year 2018-19 of observation basis T₇ sorghum + vermicompost, 155.10 spores/ml, T₆ sorghum + farm yard manure (FYM) 118.19 spores/ml, T₁ maize + farm yard manure (FYM) 104.70 spores/ml, T₈ sorghum + cow dung (fresh) 82.70 spores/ml, T₂ maize +

vermicompost 76.15 spores/ml, T₃ maize + cow dung (fresh) 71.10 spores/ml, T₁₀ sorghum + molasses 57.15 spores/ml, T₅ maize + molasses 47.15 spores/ml, T₉ sorghum + cow urine 27.15 spores/ml, T₄ maize + cow urine 38.70 spores/ml, and T₁₁ sorghum + corcyra rearing waste material of sorghum (check) 33.45 spores/ml, during the year 2019-20 respectively.

Overall result showed that 21 days among the liquid media tested, *Metarhizium anisopliae* spore/ml production was significantly recorded higher 154.68 and 119.60 spore/ml were recorded on sabouraud dextrose broth (SDB) and potato dextrose broth (PDB). Our finding showed that twenty eight days after inoculation trend during the year 2018-19 of observation basis on all substrates *i.e.* T₇ sorghum + vermicompost, 230.40 spores/ml, T₆ sorghum + farm yard manure (FYM) 197.11 spores/ml, T₁ maize + farm yard manure (FYM) 161.50 spores/ml, T₈ sorghum + cow dung (fresh) 127.50 spores/ml, T₂ maize + vermicompost 100.18 spores/ml, T₃ maize + cow dung (fresh) 89.15 spores/ml, T₁₀ sorghum + molasses 76.18 spores/ml, T₅ maize + molasses 65.15 spores/ml, T₉ sorghum + cow urine 26.17 spores/ml, T₄ maize + cow urine 51.50 spores/ml, and T₁₁ sorghum + corcyra rearing. Waste material of sorghum (check) 37.66 spores/ml, during the year 2018-19 respectively. Our finding overall result showed that on 28 days among the liquid media tested, *Metarhizium anisopliae* spore/ml production was significantly recorded higher 230.40 and 197.11 spore/ml were recorded on savoured dextrose broth (SDB) and potato dextrose broth (PDB).

Among the different substrates on thirty five days after inoculation slow growth of *Metarhizium anisopliae* spore/ml count with different significantly from the substrate T₇ sorghum + vermicompost again was the most effective treatment (240.53 spore/ml) producing. The second most effective treatment was, T₆ sorghum + farm yard manure (FYM) 223.60 spores/ml, T₁ maize + farm yard manure (FYM) 170.88 spores/ml, T₈ sorghum + cow dung (fresh) 140.70 spores/ml, T₂ maize + vermicompost 108.70 spores/ml, T₃ maize + cow dung (fresh) 98.17 spores/ml, T₁₀ sorghum + molasses 88.70 spores/ml, T₅ maize + molasses 74.80 spores/ml, T₉ sorghum + cow urine 37.80 spores/ml, T₄ maize + cow urine 50.70 spores/ml, and T₁₁ sorghum + corcyra rearing waste material of sorghum (check) 46.70 spores/ml, during the

year 2019-20 respectively. Overall finding showed that in the table-3. at 35 days among the substrate tested, for *Metarhizium anisopliae* spore/ml production was significantly higher recorded 240.53 and 195.26 spore/ml were recorded on substrate.

The present results are in conformity with the findings of (Yadav *et al.*, 2013, Prasad and Pal, 2014), Kruger Raúl Daniel *et al.*, 2014, Anitha S. *et al.*, 2015, Lioudmila Ibrahim *et al.*, 2015, Maina U. M. *et al.*, 2018, Navdeep Kaur and Neelam Joshi,

2018, Preen *et al.*, 1985, Jenkins Nina E. *et al.*, 1998, Wadyalkar S. R. *et al.*, 2003, Kumar *et al.*, 2007, Soundarapandian and Chandra, 2007, Babu *et al.*, 2008, Vijayavani *et al.*, 2010, Mehta *et al.*, 2012, Bahar Rad and Majid Amani, 2014, Anitha S., *et al.*, 2015, Nikit A. S. Awasthi *et al.*, 2017, K. D. Tekam, N. M. Kelwatkar and S. B. Das, 2018, Agale S. V. *et al.*, 2018, Neelesh Raypuriya *et al.*, 2019, Manu C. R. *et al.*, 2019).

Table 1. Multiplication of *Metarhizium anisopliae* on different media

Treatments	Substrates	Spore Concentration	At Different Days After Inoculation				
			7 DAI	14 DAI	21 DAI	28 DAI	35 DAI
T ₁	Maize + Farm yard manure (FYM)	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	7.25 (2.92)	15.37 (4.12)	46.92 (7.85)	64.28 (8.95)	75.99 (8.90)
T ₂	Maize + Vermicompost	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	11.95 (6.60)	25.33 (9.90)	55.96 (11.38)	75.85 (14.60)	87.62 (17.28)
T ₃	Maize + Cow Dung (Fresh)	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	5.25 (4.58)	4.45 (7.78)	26.30 (10.92)	27.96 (13.22)	36.38 (16.70)
T ₄	Maize + Cow Urine	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	15.87 (6.80)	39.41 (9.25)	70.51 (12.30)	91.20 (15.55)	99.25 (18.80)
T ₅	Maize + Molasses	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	19.40 (7.20)	48.25 (10.85)	74.75 (13.63)	101.95 (16.22)	108.9 (19.38)
T ₆	Sorghum +Farm yard manure (FYM)	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	2.95 (4.40)	8.67 (7.83)	32.60 (10.61)	38.59 (13.44)	47.76 (16.85)
T ₇	Sorghum + Vermicompost	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	23.52 (7.85)	60.05 (10.82)	83.68 (13.59)	126.90 (16.27)	140.35 (19.85)
T ₈	Sorghum + Cow dung (Fresh)	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	29.82 (8.45)	70.26 (11.46)	102.30 (14.11)	155.88 (17.46)	166.28 (20.85)
T ₉	Sorghum + Cow Urine	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	4.92 (4.95)	16.66 (7.88)	39.40 (10.48)	50.30 (13.95)	58.45 (16.45)
T ₁₀	Sorghum + Molasses	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	51.35 (10.20)	88.25 (13.30)	154.68 (16.40)	227.69 (19.22)	239.27 (22.45)
T ₁₁	Sorghum + Corcyra rearing Waste material of Sorghum (Check)	1x10 ⁷ spores/ ml	39.45 (9.29)	75.70 (11.59)	119.60 (14.88)	195.26 (17.95)	220.64 (20.80)
SEm ±			0.099	0.207	0.153	0.223	0.079
CD at 5%			0.297	0.417	0.436	0.463	0.235

Tewelde Abiy and Tesfaye Alemu (2019) evaluated most appropriate medium for the production of T₇ sorghum + vermicompost, T₆ sorghum + farm yard manure (FYM), T₁ maize + farm yard manure (FYM), T₈ sorghum + cow dung (fresh), T₂ maize + vermicompost, T₃ maize + cow dung (fresh), T₁₀ sorghum + molasses, T₅ maize + molasses, T₉ sorghum + cow urine, T₄ maize + cow urine, and T₁₁ sorghum + corcyra rearing. Waste material of sorghum (check) spores /ml, mass production of two entomopathogenic fungi: *Vuellemin* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* substrate for spore production and their (Yadav *et al.*, 2013, Prasad and Pal, 2014, Kruger Raúl Daniel *et al.*, 2014, Anitha S. *et al.*, 2015, Lioudmila Ibrahim *et*

al., 2015, Maina U. M. *et al.*, 2018, Navdeep Kaur and Neelam Joshi, 2018, Preen *et al.*, 1985, Jenkins Nina E. *et al.*, 1998, Wadyalkar S. R. *et al.*, 2003, Kumar *et al.*, 2007, Soundarapandian and Chandra, 2007, Babu *et al.*, 2008, Vijayavani *et al.*, 2010, Mehta *et al.*, 2012, Anitha S. *et al.*, 2015, Nikit A. S. Awasthi *et. al.*, 2017, K. D. Tekam, N. M. Kelwatkar and S. B. Das, 2018, Agale S. V. *et al.*, 2018, Neelesh Raypuriya *et al.*, 2019, Manu C. R. *et al.*, 2019). Tewelde Abiy and Tesfaye Alemu (2019) reported that, wheat supported maximum spore production for recorded maximum spore production in different medium.

Conclusion

The study revealed that all substrata support growth of *Metarhizium anisopliae* spore/ml was significantly higher recorded showed that in the results revealed that all the treatments were significantly producing spore per ml and thus increasing the yield significantly as compared to other substrates. The results revealed that all the treatments were significantly higher effective in producing spore/ml as compared to other substrates. Sorghum + vermicompost, was the best treatment by bringing down the *M. anisopliae* production up to (50.20) spore/ml in liquid medium during the 2018-19 years. Followed by sorghum + vermicompost, 50.20spores/ml and sorghum + farm yard manure (FYM) 40.15 spores/ml, T₁ maize + farm yard manure (FYM) 28.10 spores/ml.

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